

RADIOGRAPHIC STUDY OF CRANIAL STRUCTURES IN MALE HARD GROUND SWAMP DEER (*R. duvacelii branderi*)

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Abstract

The phenotypic appearance of the head of animal species significantly depends on the shape of the skull. There is scanty information on the skull morphology of barasingha deer thus, the present study was carried out on radiographic characteristics of the skull of male barasingha deer, thereby making a contribution in filling the gap of knowledge in this field. In many vetero-legal cases, the bones of this species are frequently confused with those of other small wild herbivores. Understanding the radiographic features of the skull is crucial for both surgical treatment of pathological disorders and taxonomic affiliation. Both field and zoo veterinarians will benefit from this investigation.

Keywords: Skull, Radiographic, Swamp deer, Barasingha

Introduction

Barasingha (*Rucervus duvaucelii branderi*), commonly known as the hard ground swamp deer, is a cervid of the Indian subcontinent's swampy grasslands and floodplains. The species is categorized as Vulnerable on the IUCN Red List, protected under Schedule I of the Indian Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972, and listed in Appendix-I of CITES, reflecting its high conservation priority. Three subspecies are currently recognized- *R. d. duvaucelii*, *R. d. branderi*, and *R. d. ranjitsinhi* with the hard ground form centered in central India and closely associated with Kanha National Park, where it is often celebrated as the "jewel of Kanha." Barasingha in hindi means twelve-pointer, indicating a characteristic antler pattern in adult stags with a crown of 5 tines about halfway up the antler beam in addition to the brow tine, which branches off at a right angle. This results in a total of 12 tines for both antlers. With a global population of less than 5000, the species has a very limited distribution spanning over 2,000 km² in India and Nepal (Qureshi *et al.*, 2004) due to the expansion of agriculture, loss of habitat and various other land use practices (Midha and Mathur, 2010).

Material and method

The proposed work was carried out at the School of Wildlife Forensic and Health, N.D.V.S.U., Jabalpur, (M.P.). The present study was conducted on 4 skulls of male hard ground swamp deer (*R. duvacelii branderi*), procured from Kanha national park of Madhya Pradesh. The skulls were de-skinned and kept under maceration for a period of one month. The attachment of skulls was removed after maceration and whitening of skulls was done by treating the skulls with 3% hydrogen peroxide. Then, the radiographic imaging of skull of barasingha deer was performed by taking X-ray from different views and radiographic features of ventrodorsal surface and lateral surface of male adult skull bones of barasingha deer was recorded.

Result and discussion**Ventrodorsal radiographic observation**

The ventrodorsal radiographic view of the skull of male barasingha deer was dolichocephalic type and elongated (Fig 01) coincides with the findings of Kumawat (2011) in chital deer; Choudhary *et al.* (2015) in blackbuck, Keneisenuo *et al.* (2022) in barking deer and sambar deer and Lade (2022); however, it was brachiocephalic type in the tiger as reported by Joshi (2005). This radiographic view reveals radiopaque radiograph due to higher density of bone of male barasingha deer. The bones of the base of cranium (occipital, sphenoid and ethmoid) were more radiopaque than the temporal and frontal bone and bones of lateral wall (temporal, frontal and maxilla bone) was highly radiolucent indicating the less density of bone. The cranial cavity was marked as ovoid shadow; occipital condyle and foramen magnum was clearly visible similar with the finding of Kumawat (2011) in chital, they were located caudo-ventrally and medially to the internal acoustic meatus are in correlation with the findings of Archana *et al.* (1997) in yak and Kumawat (2011) in chital. The posterior margin of foramen magnum was occupied by supraoccipital bone. The external acoustic meatus was seen as a blackspot due to presence of air density. The zygomatic arch was extended laterally and appeared as a flattened radiopaque plate in accordance with Lade (2022) in male chital and sambar deer. The turbinates were radiopaque was clearly visible as reported by Keneisenuo *et al.* (2022) in male sambar and barking deer and Lade (2022) in male sambar and chital deer. The tympanic bulla was also visible because the shadow of dense petrous temporal bone overlapped the tympanic bulla and produced a white area in ventral projections. Premaxilla bone was radiopaque and present in the form of plate like (Fig 01).

Fig 01: Radiographic ventral view of skull of male barasingha deer showing Foramen magnum (A); Zygomatic arch (B); First, second and third superior molar tooth (C); First, second and third superior premolar tooth (D); Nasal canal (E); Nasal turbinate (F); Palatine fissure (G); Incisive bone (H) and Inter incisive fissure (I)

Lateral radiographic observation

In lateral view, the skull shows all bony structures in cranial and facial region were temporal fossa, occipital condyle, paramastoid process, nasal bone, nasal turbinate, nasal cavity, incisive bone, maxillary sinus, frontal sinus and orbit was seen (Fig 02). The nasal cavity was larger and clearly visible. It was divided by a nasal septum similar with the finding of Kumawat (2011) in chital deer and Joshi *et al.* (2005) in tiger. Turbinate bones were clearly visible; there were two dorsal and two ventral turbinates on each side of nasal cavity. The first, second and third superior premolar tooth; first, second and third superior molar

tooth were linearly arranged, the crown root and pulp cavity of tooth were clearly visualized. The lacrimal fissure is also clear visible. The frontal sinus and maxillary sinus were observed clearly. The lateral plate of incisive bone was curved, paramastoid process was radiopaque similar with the finding of Lade (2022). The orbital region of the skull was overlapped partly by the frontal sinus. The frontal crest was concave and cornual process was highly radiopaque. The cornual processes were directed caudo-dorsally in its origin over the temporal fossa. Radiograph shows deep lacrimal pit in male barasingha deer (Fig 02).

Fig 02: Radiographic lateral view of the skull of male barasingha deer showing Nasal bone (A); Nasal turbinate (B); Nasal cavity (C); Incisive bone (D); First, second and third superior premolar tooth (E); First, second and third superior molar tooth (F); Paramastoid process (G); Occipital condyle (H); Temporal fossa (I); Maxillary sinus(J); Frontal sinus (K) and Orbit (L)

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